

“MAGISTRLAR” CERTIFICATE OF AWARD

We hereby present this certificate to

Кочкарова С.А.

INTERESTING PROBLEMS OF TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANDI

